

Corrosion fatigue model development for tailor-made S-N curves for offshore wind turbine foundations

A deterministic approach

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ABSTRACT

Design against fatigue is in many cases the governing criterion for dimensioning offshore wind turbine foundations. Corrosion, and in particular local deep and relatively sharp corrosion pits, affects the fatigue life of the steel components. Corrosion mitigation methods are typically evaluated in the design to reduce the effect of corrosion. Localised corrosion and specifically the effect of pit growth on the fatigue life is typically not included in structural design standards. This paper presents a deterministic corrosion fatigue model and life prediction method that includes fatigue crack initiation in a corrosion pit and the crack propagation life. With the corrosion fatigue model, S-N curves are derived for the relevant input parameters of various conditions and scenarios, which is a simplified representation of the outcome, but enables comparing these to the S-N curves adopted by the DNV-RP-C203, typically used in design. This comparison shows that the DNV-RP-C203 S-N curves are conservative for a number of cycles $\geq 10^7$, although this strongly depends on the input parameters used in the developed corrosion fatigue model.

Keywords: corrosion, fatigue, offshore wind turbine foundations, cathodic protection

1 INTRODUCTION

Design of offshore wind turbine foundations, such as monopiles, is often governed by fatigue, due to the dynamic wave and wind loading, and rotation of the wind turbine blades. S-N curves are typically used in the design to quantify the effect of fluctuating loads on the fatigue life. During operation, offshore wind turbines are exposed to harsh environmental conditions, such as a corrosion in sea water. Material degradation due to corrosion occurs at small (local) scale and uniform over larger surfaces. Localised corrosion is a dangerous form of corrosion, because it (i) is hard to detect, (ii) is hard to predict the location of formation, and (iii) may act as a local stress raiser in a structural component already at minimum material loss, for instance due to a (combination of) pit(s). Due to the latter, in combination with fluctuating loads, fatigue cracks can initiate sooner in the presence of corrosion, especially local corrosion. Corrosion mitigation techniques such as coatings and cathodic protection (CP) using galvanic anodes or an impressed current are typically applied on wind turbine foundation structures to prevent or reduce corrosion. To account for the effect of these corrosion mitigation techniques on fatigue, DNV-RP-C203 (1) provides S-N curves for offshore steel structures for three different environments, in descending order of fatigue strength: (i) air (also used for coated steel), (ii) sea water with CP, and (iii) sea water with free corrosion. Sea water environment S-N curves are based on fatigue tests on small-scale specimens submerged in sea water. Due to test restraints, limited pre-corrosion before and limited exposure time during fatigue testing, typically the (local) corrosion in the specimens is not fully representative of practical conditions expected in offshore wind turbine foundations. Because it is very complex or time-consuming to match the

corrosion rate (of pits) in fatigue tests with practice, (analytic) models are necessary to understand the combined degradation mechanisms and determine the effect of (localised) corrosion on the fatigue life of steel structures.

Larrosa et al. (2) concluded that corrosion fatigue can be split up into four phases, as shown in Figure 1. The pit-to-crack transition phase indicates the transition from the time dependent process of corrosion, to the cycles dependent process of fatigue. This phase is not yet fully understood, since it is hard to grasp the transition in experiments or models. Burns et al. (3) attempted to capture fatigue crack initiation from corrosion pits induced by pre-corroding the specimens. By using surface profile measurements, and analysing the corrosion pits in Finite Element (FE) models, Burns et al. concluded that the pit-to-crack transition depends on four factors: (i) micro-, and macro-topography (e.g. surface roughness, pit shape, pit depth), (ii) local plasticity (a driving force for fatigue crack initiation in general), (iii) hydrogen embrittlement (causes brittle fracture), and (iv) chemical processes (although unclear to what extent). The combination of all these factors, make the pit-to-crack transition a very complex phenomenon to quantify. Turnbull et al. (4), Fatoba (5) and Cerit et al. (6) performed FE analysis of various shaped (combinations of) corrosion pits showing the dependency of the stress and strain distribution on the pit shape and configuration. Coupon exposure tests to determine corrosion rates have been performed by Melchers (7) (8) (9), Wang et al. (10), and Khodabux et al. (11) (12) for different steel types, environmental conditions, and exposure periods. The field and tests show that corrosion is prone to many different parameters. Fatoba (5) and Zhao et al. (13) show an increase of corrosion rate with applied stress, although the effect of (cyclic) stress on localised corrosion is not fully understood and hard to quantify from experiments. Lackey (14) and Chaves (15) show that welded material is found to be prone to larger corrosion rates than base material. Another knowledge gap is the effect of micro-biologically influenced corrosion (MIC) in the environment applicable to offshore wind turbine foundations. From tests in lab conditions, MIC can be quantified, but it is unknown whether the mechanism is representative for field conditions, and from field tests it is unknown whether MIC was the driving mechanism for corrosion pit formation.

Figure 1 Phases of corrosion fatigue, from Larrosa et al. (2).

This paper focusses on the development of a deterministic corrosion fatigue model incorporating localised corrosion, fatigue crack initiation and fatigue crack propagation. The model is applied to different corrosion mitigation strategies for S355 steel monopile foundations in sea water to develop tailor-made S-N curves.

The first studies attempting to predict the fatigue life of structures including the effect of corrosion pit growth were based on LFM, regarding the corrosion pit as a large crack. One of the best known

approaches is the competition model of Kondo (16), in which a critical pit condition $(\Delta K)_p$ is defined, at which the crack growth rate equals the pit growth rate. Below this value, a pit growth equation should be applied, above this value LEFM. Another approach quantifies a threshold SIF ΔK_{th} purely based on experiments. Other studies, such as Schönbauer et al. (17), regarded the corrosion pit as a small crack, and implemented a short crack growth threshold based on e.g. El Haddad et al. (18). Another option is the stress- or strain-based approach. Then, the pit-to-crack transition is estimated based on the stress or strain concentration in an (idealized) corrosion pit, which can be based on FE models or analytic stress concentration factors (SCFs). Next, the stress or strain concentration is used to determine the number of cycles to fatigue crack initiation N_i using S-N curves (19) (5), or by using the strain-life curve from low cycle fatigue (LCF) tests (20). A completely different approach is using continuum damage mechanics (21) to estimate the fatigue crack initiation life from corrosion pits, such as applied by Yin et al. (22). In this approach, still an S-N like relation between stress or (plastic) strain and number of cycles to failure is necessary to be able to accumulate damage. Recent research by Okenyi et al. (23) presented a corrosion fatigue model for offshore welded structures of S355 steel, based on the endurance limit approach and includes the effect of corrosion pits using correction factors. The method appears to perform well in comparison to experiments where corrosion is often limited, but does not include growing pits.

2 CORROSION FATIGUE MODEL APPROACH

2.1 Outline

The deterministic corrosion fatigue model developed in this study incorporates (i) corrosion pit development, (ii) fatigue crack initiation from the single or double corrosion pits, including the presence of micro-pits, and (iii) fatigue crack propagation until fracture of the rest ligament. Figure 2 presents the outline of the developed deterministic corrosion fatigue model. On the left side, all input parameters are given. The right side includes all steps in the model, divided into a fatigue crack initiation life module and a fatigue crack propagation life module. The fatigue crack initiation life module consists of an iterative calculation for simultaneous fatigue loading and corrosion pit growth, because the corrosion pit size affects the fatigue damage accumulation. The fatigue crack initiation life module consists of a single calculation when a static corrosion pit is assessed. Assumptions in the corrosion process are discussed in Section 2.2. In the model, the strain-life relation is used to determine fatigue crack initiation life and therefore the moment of the pit-to-crack transition. During short crack growth, the microstructure still plays an important role (24), which makes this phase complex to model. Therefore, in agreement with Schijve (25), the initiation period can be assumed to end when the fatigue crack growth is no longer depending on material surface conditions. This means that the short crack growth is included in the fatigue crack initiation life, and therefore the strain-life curve can be used to estimate the fatigue crack initiation life. Other assumptions and input parameters for determination of the fatigue crack initiation lifetime are discussed in Section 2.3. Subsequently, the fatigue crack propagation module is initiated using the final corrosion pit size as initial crack size, or an initial crack depth of $a_{c,i} = 0.15\text{mm}$ if the corrosion pit is smaller. In the fatigue crack propagation phase, the crack growth rate increases continuously with crack length. Linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) can be used to estimate the fatigue crack propagation life. LEFM assumes a (bi-)linear crack growth relation, such as the Paris' equation (26), and assesses the crack using stress intensity factor (SIF) range ΔK . Assumptions in the determination of the fatigue crack propagation lifetime are discussed in Section 2.4.

Figure 2 Model outline

2.2 Corrosion process

General corrosion rates and local corrosion shapes and rates were derived from field data of coupons exposed inside monopiles received in the C-FLO project (confidential), literature on field data of coupon exposures (12) (15), exposure tests in lab conditions performed in the project (confidential), and DNV-RP-0416 (27). It is found that the corrosion rates differ in the various locations in the monopile. Therefore, different zones are introduced in Figure 3. Table 1 presents the assumed corrosion rates per zone for base material. It is assumed that the corrosion rates (both uniform as localised) are linear in the first three years, after which a slight exponential decay of the localised corrosion rate is assumed. It is assumed that MIC can occur in the submerged zone and top 3m of the buried zone, and it is assumed to take 0.5 year for the micro-organisms to form a colony and create an environment that significantly increases the corrosion rate. For the splash & tidal zone, a differentiation is made between the environment in- and outside the monopile. It is assumed that cathodic protection fully stops the corrosion process. For heat affected zone (HAZ) material, an increase of the average corrosion rate by 60% is assumed based on tests by Chaves and Melchers (15).

Figure 3 Monopile zones. MP=monopile, HAT=highest astronomical tide, LAT=lowest astronomical tide, MWL=mean waterline.

Table 1 Assumed corrosion rates without mitigation measures for base material

Zone	Corrosion rate [mm/yr]	
	General corrosion	Localised corrosion
Atmospheric zone	0.05	0.15
Splash & tidal zone	External	0.25
	Internal	0.15
Submerged zone	0.10	First 0.5 year: 0.15, after 0.5 year: 0.50 (MIC)
Top 3m of buried zone	0.03	First 0.5 year: 0.15, after 0.5 year: 0.50 (MIC)
Buried zone	0.03	0.08

Localised corrosion is simplified to semi-elliptical notches with an aspect ratio $AR_p = a_p/2c_p$, see Figure 4, that is assumed to remain constant in time. To include roughness and secondary pits, so-called “micro-pits” are included. Corrosion pits often grow in vicinity of another, which can result in increased stress concentrations when pits are in close vicinity. This effect is simplified by incorporating the stress increase due to a maximum of two equal-sized corrosion pits in close vicinity, with an initial edge-to-edge distance $s_{e,e,i}$. Due to imperfections and possible defects along welds, it

is assumed for both flush ground welds and as-welded condition, that an initial defect due to manufacturing is present of $a_{p,i} = 0.15\text{mm}$.

Figure 4 Corrosion pit geometry definitions. (a) shows the definition of distance y , used determining the location of initiation for growing pits, (b) shows the definition of different pit configurations: single pit with micro-pit and double pit centre-to-centre distance.

Table 2 Input parameters for the semi-elliptical pit geometry

Input parameter	Symbol	Value
Pit aspect ratio [-]	AR_p	0.40
Micro-pit to macro-pit depth ratio [-]	a_{micro}/a_p	0.10
Micro-pit aspect ratio [-]	$AR_{p,micro}$	0.40
Initial pits edge-to-edge distance [mm]	$s_{ee,i}$	Most favourable position for fatigue crack initiation

2.3 Fatigue crack initiation model

Using FE analysis, the stress distribution around the corrosion pits of different aspect ratios and distances to other corrosion pits is determined. Using superposition, also the effect of a micro-pit has been incorporated. Based on the SCF and stress gradient at a certain location, a fatigue notch factor K_f has been determined including the effect of a weld toe if present. The weld toe SCF is based on Anthes et al. (28) (29), and the stress gradient on an elliptical notch as given by Schijve (25). Subsequently, the load spectrum is multiplied by the fatigue notch factor, and the local elastic and plastic strain is determined using Neuber's stress correction (30). Subsequently, the strain-life relation determined using the Basquin (31) and Coffin-Manson (32) (33) equation is used including mean stress correction by Morrow (34), see Eq. (1), in which the fatigue strength coefficient σ'_f is reduced by the mean stress σ_0 . The input parameters for the Coffin-Manson relation are based on Bignonnet et al. (35) (36), and presented in Table 3. A standard deviation of $s_{logN} = 0.20$ is used based on S-N curve standard deviation (1) because the amount of data is too limited to determine a representative standard deviation. It is uncertain what the crack size was at the number of cycles reported by Bignonnet et al.; in this study, it is assumed that it is approximately $a_{c,i} = 0.15\text{ mm}$, meaning that it includes short crack growth. Damage is accumulated using Miners' Rule (37).

$$\frac{\Delta\varepsilon}{2} = \frac{(\sigma'_f - \sigma_0)}{E} (2N)^b + \varepsilon'_f (2N)^c \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Table 3 Strain-life parameters (mean) for fatigue crack initiation in different environments (35) (36)

Environment	σ'_f [MPa]	b [-]	ε'_f [-]	c [-]
Air	1091	-0.129	1.898	-0.746
Seawater free corrosion	1137	-0.124	1.415	-0.769
Seawater CP -800 mV	999	-0.109	0.854	-0.654

2.4 Fatigue crack propagation model

At the moment of the pit-to-crack transition, LEFM is used to determine the crack propagation life. LEFM is valid for long cracks, and often an initial crack size of $a_{c,i} = 0.1 - 0.15\text{mm}$ is used. In this study, it is conservatively assumed that the initial crack size equals the corrosion pit size at the moment of the pit-to-crack transition, because the stress concentration due to the corrosion pit is not included in the fatigue crack propagation life:

$$a_{c,i} = \max(0.15\text{mm}, a_p) \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

BS7910 (38) presents a complete set of crack propagation parameters using a bi-linear Paris' equation for sea water, CP, and air conditions, and is used in this study. To account for residual stresses at weld locations, the parameters for a high stress ratio ($R \geq 0.5$) are considered. The failure criterion is assumed as $a_f = 0.6T$ (T equals wall thickness), which is a rough assumption, but probably with little impact because cracks at this size expand rapidly.

2.5 Corrosion mitigation

Two different corrosion mitigation techniques are regarded in this study: an impressed current cathodic protection (ICCP) system set to -800 mV vs Ag/AgCl , and a coating system. For both, it is assumed that it fully stops corrosion as long as the system is active or coating is intact. It is assumed that free corrosion occurs during the period between installation of the monopile and activation of the ICCP system when no coating is applied. It is also assumed that the tower is installed on the monopile at the same moment as installation of the ICCP system. This study focusses on S-N curves during operation, and therefore any fatigue damage during pile driving or in the period before installation of the tower is neglected.

3 RESULTS

Validation of the complete corrosion fatigue model is complex, because the effect of (localised) corrosion in fatigue tests is limited. Nevertheless, DNV-RP-C203 presents S-N curves for air, CP, and free corrosion (FC) conditions, and a comparison to these S-N curves is made to partly validate the model. The comparison includes flush ground welds (DNV C1-category), and as-welded butt welds (DNV D-category). It is concluded that not a single representative S-N curve for the complete lifetime of the structure could be established for each free corrosion condition, because the (local) structural condition of the monopile is continuously changing in time due to the corrosion process, and the S-N curve captures only a single structural condition. Therefore, this paragraph only shows results for CP and coating systems. Results are shown for the submerged zone in the monopile, since this zone yields the largest corrosion rate.

Figure 5 presents the results of the corrosion fatigue model for flush ground welds and as-welded condition in the submerged zone including a CP system installed after 6 months. A double pit configuration in worst combination (highest SCF) is considered. The figure shows that the fatigue crack initiation life dominates the fatigue life of flush ground welds for $\geq 10^7$ cycles, where for the as-welded condition, the fatigue crack initiation life is significantly lower due to the high SCF of the weld toe. The fatigue crack propagation life is in good agreement with the DNV S-N curves, as expected. The addition of fatigue crack initiation life in the corrosion fatigue model shows potential in the high and giga-cycle cycle fatigue region ($\geq 10^7$ cycles) where limited test data for establishing S-N curves is available. But, also limited LCF test data for the strain-life curve is available in this region, which is used for calculating the fatigue crack initiation life.

Figure 5 Corrosion fatigue model results (a) flush ground welds, (b) as-welded in the submerged zone including a CP system installed after 6 months (resulting in $a_{p,i} = 0.34\text{mm}$). Design curves are shown (mean- $2S_{\log N}$) with double pit configuration.

Figure 6 presents the increase of the fatigue strength due to coating or CP system, and decrease with the period between installation of the monopile and activation of the CP system. The difference between the S-N curve for coating conditions and the S-N curve for CP conditions with 1 month between installation of the monopile and activation of the CP system appears to be significant in Figure 6a, even though the difference in initial corrosion pit is small ($a_{p,i} = 0.15\text{mm}$ versus 0.17mm). This difference is explained by the use of the strain-life curve in air conditions for coating conditions, which results in a larger fatigue crack initiation life than the strain-life curve in sea water conditions with CP.

Figure 6 Corrosion fatigue model results (a) flush ground welds, (b) as-welded in the submerged zone for coating & CP conditions. Design curves are shown (mean- $2S_{\log N}$) with double pit configuration.

Figure 7 shows the effect of corrosion pit configuration on the fatigue strength. The figure shows that micro-pits decrease the fatigue crack initiation life, but the fatigue crack propagation life remains equal due to the assumption that short crack growth is included in initiation life. The orange S-N curve for a single pit is not visible in Figure 7b, but is equal to the green S-N curve for a single pit including micro-pit. This shows that micro-pits have no effect on pits at weld toe of as-welded welds, because the initiation position is at the weld toe, not at the micro-pit, due to a larger fatigue notch factor at the weld toe than at the micro-pit location.

Figure 7 Corrosion fatigue model results showing the effect of pit configuration for (a) flush ground welds, (b) as-welded in the submerged zone for coating & CP conditions. Design curves are shown (mean- $2S_{\log N}$).

4 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The following conclusions are drawn:

- Corrosion fatigue is a complex process that is dependent on a large amount of input parameters that do not all act independent of another.
- The amount of corrosion in fatigue tests in seawater is very limited and not fully representative of practical conditions; therefore, analytic models are required to assess the effect of corrosion on the fatigue life of structures.
- Localised corrosion, such as corrosion pits, decreases the fatigue strength.
- The total fatigue lifetime of a component in free corrosion conditions cannot accurately be captured in a single S-N curve based on a deterministic corrosion fatigue model as developed in this study, because the structural condition is continuously changing in time.
- The developed corrosion fatigue model enables quantifying the effect of corrosion mitigation measures and environmental conditions. The model shows that the DNV-RP-C203 is conservative in the high cycle fatigue and giga-cycle domains ($\geq 10^7$ cycles), although this strongly depends on the input parameters.

Continuation of this work will include:

- The strain-life relation for S355 steel in different environmental conditions is not well-defined in the high cycle fatigue region. More test data on fatigue crack initiation in this region is required.
- The strain-life relation used in this study is for a surface defect, but is also used for determining the fatigue damage below the material surface. A strain-life relation for a below-the-surface defect should be implemented if available.
- To fully grasp all stages of the fatigue process, the short crack growth phase should be explicitly included in the model.
- Application of the developed deterministic corrosion fatigue model in a probabilistic framework to determine S-N curves based on stochastic input parameters.

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